

Assessment of Quipper as Learning Management System of Saint Paul University Surigao

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ABSTRACT: A school learning management system (LMS) is extremely important in the current educational landscape since it transforms how educational institutions administer and deliver their courses. LMS gives educators a strong platform to produce, organize, and distribute instructional content while enabling students to access resources, participate in interactive learning activities, and collaborate with peers by seamlessly integrating technology into the learning process. This study was conducted to assess the level of utilization, level of satisfaction, and level of effectiveness with Quipper as an LMS in Saint Paul University Surigao (SPUS), Surigao City, Philippines. The research design was quantitative, and researchers used a survey questionnaire to gather data from the college faculty of SPUS during the academic year 2022-2023. To ensure reliable results, 33 college teachers were purposefully and conveniently chosen as respondents. The data were analyzed using various parametric and non-parametric statistical tools considering the normality of the data. The study revealed that variables such as sex, age, department, highest educational attainment, and years of teaching experience did not significantly impact Quipper's utilization and satisfaction among teachers. The profile of college faculty members also did not significantly affect Quipper's effectiveness as a learning management system. However, the department variable significantly influenced Quipper's performance, with frequent utilization leading to higher satisfaction and effectiveness. Overall, Quipper was widely used, effective, and met the needs of the college faculty at SPUS. The study suggested room for improvement, and the administration could establish clear implementation goals, offer incentives to consistent users, provide proper training and guidance, and encourage teachers to explore more features to better support students' learning.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation, Effectiveness, E-learning, Flexible Learning, Satisfaction, Utilization.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The COVID-19 pandemic changed the way people go through their lives in more ways than one, including the disruption of the educational system which affected more than 60% of students [1]. Face-to-face classes must be stopped and so, students and teachers continued instructing from the confine of their own homes through online learning. Schools, their administrators, teachers, and students must adapt to the digitalization of education delivery using a Learning Management System or LMS [2]. A learning management system (LMS) is a software web-based technology, that is used to plan, implement, and evaluate learning processes via online distance learning [3]. With LMS, teachers learn how to create and deliver content, assess student participation, and evaluate performance' achievement. Students, on the other hand, use LMS to access interactive tools like discussion boards, video conferencing, and threaded discussions.

As of now, the Philippines introduced Education 4.0, in which there will be a path for students to follow to be ready for the future as well as ensures that teaching-learning experiences take advantage of the endless possibilities provided by advanced technology [4,5]. They would attain 21st-century skills and learn more for conceptual clarity than just be limited to learning for exams. Currently, the world is experiencing some significant changes. A dynamic and ever-evolving educational model is built on the activities of learning that students engage in and the strategies and techniques used by the teachers. The progress of this

structural innovation process to the current Education 4.0 has been focused on the advancement and transformation of science and technology throughout time.

One of the prestigious schools in the CARAGA region is St. Paul University Surigao which marked differences among schools, a Catholic basic and higher education institution run by the Sisters of St. Paul of Chartres in Surigao City. They pursue a more adaptive and inclusive Flexible Distance Learning Education System. Distance learning is an educational process where students receive instruction through online classes, video recordings, video conferencing, or any other audio/visual technology medium. It enables people to receive an education without having to be physically present in a classroom [6]. Especially, St. Paul University Surigao used Quipper as a web-based online learning application for teachers and students.

Through these methods, more flexible, user-friendly, and easily accessible ways of learning are achieved. Still, there are challenges encountered in implementing these strategies to facilitate learning. There comes the problem of not having adequate technological resources to make use of the applications, as well as the intermittent connections in areas around the country that further make the activity of learning extra tedious and challenging. From this notion, the need to understand the utilization, satisfaction, and effectiveness of learning management systems arises.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

This study was anchored on the concept of a Learning Management System studied by Kasim and Khalid [7]. Learning Management System (LMS) is an e-learning tool widely used to improve students' learning experience and construct their understanding of specific topics. It is a system used to provide students with learning materials and activities while tracking participation and progress through data systems and assessments [8].

Moreover, the adoption rate of LMS in academic and training institutions is promising worldwide. The learning Management system includes several tools that provide academic and training institutions with efficient and effective means to support distance education and supplement their traditional way of teaching. LMS also provides theoretical implications, mechanisms, and tools to store, manage, and share its academic resources and knowledge. Instructors' acceptance is essential for the deployment of LMS. The success of LMS in any institution starts with instructors' approval, which initiates and promotes learners' utilization of LMS. [9]

On the other hand, using a learning management system in higher education is essential. Schools and institutions have used this method to assist students in learning more, exploring, and broadening their learning environment. LMS is also crucial for educators, faculty, and staff at schools. Because teachers and educators play a significant role in how well students use LMS, this study examined and evaluated the utilization, satisfaction, and effectiveness of LMS to the teachers.

1.3 Objectives

This study aimed to answer the following specific questions:

- 1.3.1 What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, department, highest educational attainment, and number of years in teaching?
- 1.3.2 What is the level of utilization, satisfaction, and effectiveness of Quipper as LMS in terms of curriculum and assignment, statistics, classlist, students, and Q-create?
- 1.3.3 Is there a significant difference in the level of utilization, satisfaction, and effectiveness of Quipper as LMS when grouped based on respondents' profile?
- 1.3.4 Is there a significant relationship among the level of utilization, satisfaction, and effectiveness of Quipper as LMS?

1.4 Literature Review

The global education system underwent changes in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and the need for distant learning. Educational institutions worldwide adopted learning management systems that use technology to support students' learning from home. It was emphasized that these learning management systems provide essential features like attendance monitoring, online testing, and in-app meeting tools for interaction with teachers and students just as they did when classes were still held in person [10]. Despite limitations, institutions have been able to maintain a high level of learning using the learning management system.

St. Paul University Surigao is committed to providing high-quality education and has introduced Quipper as a new learning tool [11]. However, for this tool to be effective, it is necessary for teachers to be trained in how to use it in their classes,

especially during exams. To fully embrace this change, teachers need to recognize the importance of technology in education and be willing to integrate it into their work. This may involve utilizing Quipper as a learning management system in teaching whether they like it or not because technology has an important role to play in modern education, and it is essential for teachers to adapt to this changing landscape to provide the best possible learning experience for their students. As the world continues to evolve, there is a need to adapt and strengthen teaching strategies, moving away from traditional methods and utilizing learning management system technology to support the learning process.

Learning Management System

A learning management system (LMS) is a software application used to manage and organize learning resources, student interaction, assessments, and reporting on student performance. It is web-based and can be accessed by students through web browsers on any device. The LMS includes features like portals, curriculum management, content management, and instructional management. Some schools have integrated their enrollment and monitoring systems into the LMS. The LMS provides students with access to online learning resources, course rules, assignments, grades, interaction with other students and faculty, knowledge exchange, and online tests and quizzes. The implementation of LMS has provided students with more options for engaging in online courses, either as a requirement for certification or as part of the formal curriculum [7]. Understanding the factors that influence LMS implementation and use can help with the design, development, and implementation of more effective support and training for faculty and learners [12]. Also, in 2017, faculty development was identified as the most significant concern in teaching and learning; institutional leaders recognize the importance of assisting faculty in their use of instructional technologies, particularly the LMS. [13]

Accordingly,) a standard LMS supports an inclusive learning environment for academic progress with interceding structures that promote online collaborative-groupings, professional training, discussions, and communication among other LMS users. Instructors should balance active learning with the use of LMS technological resources and the use of guidelines from the qualified curriculum. An LMS allows instructors to facilitate and model discussions, plan online activities, set learning expectations, provide learners with options, and assist in problem-solving processes for decision making. An instructor's presence within an LMS creates an engaging learning environment. Students can retain their autonomy, enthusiasm, and motivation with LMS used. [14]

Furthermore, it was revealed that LMS or Learning Management Systems have taken the role of being the frontrunners in terms of preparing students for better learning styles. Since they form part of the technological era that is currently taking the world by storm, revolutionary ways of implementing lessons and assessments have already been introduced to teachers and students alike. Before the whole world knows it, the education system will adopt the technological advancements taking place and it is a must that learning institutions learn how to fully utilize these Learning Management Systems to produce students with higher learning capacities and improved applications skills. Understanding the LMS's widespread adoption is a vital step toward understanding how faculty may choose to apply other technological and pedagogical innovations. [15]

Quipper as Learning Management System

Quipper, also known as Quipper School, is a web-based online learning tool. It was created by Quipper Ltd., a London-based company. Quipper is used by millions of teachers and students worldwide, including in the Philippines. This could help to explain why Quipper supports several languages. Quipper provides a ready-to-use online learning tool for teachers and students, unlike comparable web-based learning management platforms such as Moodle, Claroline, ATutor, Omeka, and Docebo, which require installation on an existing hosting site (or a web server). It also assists teachers by providing online storage for PowerPoint presentations, PDF files, photographs, and videos. Furthermore, the storage allows teachers to keep track of their teaching and learning activities on the web server, allowing them to monitor their students' progress without regard for time or location. It's important to note that even though registration is required, using these facilities and services in Quipper is completely free. [16]

Through Quipper School, teachers can provide their students the online assignments which can be accessed through students' mobile devices (smartphones, tablets and netbooks, personal computers), and they can also monitor their learning progress online. Students can learn wherever they want if their devices are connected to the internet. Quipper School has several important features in supporting the online history learning process. To use the Quipper School application, teachers may start by: (1) logging in using a facebook account or through manual registration, (2) creating a class with a maximum of 60 students, (3) creating a new class, then in Quipper School will give you a unique "class code". The teachers then can copy and send it to

students. Furthermore, students register and enter the class by using the access code provided by the teacher, (4) after that, both teachers and students are connected via an access code in the classroom. Quipper School has several important features, including: Quipper School Link; this feature is provided for teachers to create and manage classes online. This feature can be used by teachers who aim to provide homework, practice, and even examinations for students. This school link system provides learning materials and questions consisting of various topics for each subject. In addition, there are instrument facilities that can be used by the teacher to perform analysis functions, formative evaluation and summative evaluation such as: (a) monitoring students in learning activities (student score reports on their assignment/homework), (b) viewing data analysis/graphs of student development, (c) observing the analysis of topics that students have or have not mastered yet, (d) sending messages or responses to students' questions, (e) making announcements for students, and (f) printing the student score reports. [17]

In addition, different roles provide different access to Quipper's features. The 'teacher role' enables teachers to have full access to QS's three main features namely 'creation', 'assessment', and 'learning'. The role also grants teachers access to 'overview', 'assignments', 'curriculum', 'message' and 'manage' menus. The 'overview' menu provides brief information about active assignments submitted by the students and students' individual performances. The 'assignment' menu allows teachers to create new assignments, distribute them to students and monitor their progress. [18]

The 'curriculum' menu offers two options for teachers regarding the learning materials; they can either use the materials available on QS database, or they can develop their own materials and use them to teach their students. The 'message' menu has two functions; firstly, it facilitates teacher-student communication, and, secondly, it allows teachers to distribute notes to all students. Finally, the 'manage' menu allows teachers to select course participants, group the students, and invite other colleagues to teach collaboratively within the virtual classroom. They mentioned that the most useful feature of QS is the Assignment menu since it provides a lot of exercises for the students to practice.

Concerning the teaching materials, teachers can either use the available materials provided by Quipper or develop or upload their own materials. Having provided the materials by the website, the participants say that the materials are good and helpful. However, sometimes they combine the available materials with those they make to enrich and vary the materials. Drawing on their experience of using Quipper, the teachers commonly summarized three drawbacks of Quipper. Quipper is an internet-dependent media. Thus, the Internet connection is the main problem in utilizing the media. Secondly, extended use of online classes reduces students' actual interaction both with the teacher and their peers, in other words, the students interact only with gadgets. Finally, on one hand, QS provides a wide range of teaching materials and becomes a potential alternative teaching medium.

Furthermore, for the Quipper School, learning activities become more flexible, better done in a synchronous and an asynchronous way. In this learning management system, teachers and students have their own account. Teachers can create classes according to their subject, and students can enter the class by entering the code given by the teacher. Learning interaction can be done by visiting the link to the students about the material, tasks, and specific matters. Interactions can also be done with chat or message. Quipper School provides free facilities and learning materials in the form of various forms of articles, animations, and video tutorials. In addition to the material already available in the system, teachers can also add additional material. Quipper School is used by teachers to assist them in managing learning materials, examinations, and students' grades. Learning management systems such as Quipper have provided many benefits to teachers in the form of training. [19,20,21]

Utilization of Quipper as Learning Management System

The Philippine education system is a challenging issue as it rethinks its approach and prepares for the new normal [22]. A recent study was conducted focusing on the Utilization of Quipper Application as Learning Management System in Teaching as Experienced by the Junior High School Teachers of St. Paul University Surigao Teachers and indicated that faculty teachers highly utilized Quipper as Learning Management System in teaching in terms of Sending Assignments and Practice Examinations, Creating Educational Content and Viewing and Downloading Analytics [11]. Regarding the use of Quipper, the Department of Education in San Juan City Philippines noted that Quipper Learn and Quipper Link automatically sync student progress, giving teachers a rich source of information on their students' level of effort, attainment, strengths, and weaknesses.

In addition, the use of Quipper School has a positive impact on increasing students' interest in reading. Understanding the content of the text in each material presented, improved independent reading activities, and critical thinking skills in responding to the content of the text demonstrate an increase in students' reading interest [23]. This is evidence that students are adapting to new

changes in the educational system. As a result, online learning is becoming a huge catalyzer for people and companies to help them adopt this rapid change in the world [24]. Furthermore, the features at Quipper School make it simple for teachers to provide students with materials and tasks [25]. Students who use Quipper School will also increase their understanding of the topic to be taught and test their ability and comprehension of the information taught through the use of questions supplied by the teacher in the Quipper School's teaching materials. This instructional material can be produced by students as extra teaching resources that can be accessed at any time and from any location.

Furthermore, this application can be used to manage learning and to provide lots of free learning resources to students and teachers. According to some research on this application, there are many positive aspects that can be obtained using this application, such as student interest, learning outcomes, and learning activeness. [19]

Satisfaction of Quipper as Learning Management System

Quipper has developed into a resource for providing high-quality education in the new normal of learning. Quipper LMS has high user satisfaction since it provides significant assistance to learners who experienced difficulties during the pandemic. Quipper LMS has increased DTE students' sense of responsibility and provides a more flexible learning environment, allowing them to better manage their learning. [26]

Accordingly, Quipper School can assist both teachers and students in their teaching and learning activities. It allows teachers to spend more time outside of the classroom enhancing students' understanding of the material. Teachers and students express positive and negative perceptions. According to the teacher, the material provided is good and understandable. However, there are some materials that were not covered or were missing. The students assumed that the application aided them in gaining a deeper understanding since it included useful materials such as a video, summary, and task. Unfortunately, they discovered a flaw in the material. They claimed that the material could not be accessed offline or downloaded. [27]

From a recent study, the overall ratings of students, teachers, and administrators were all satisfied and convinced that Quipper School positively contributes to the overall teaching and learning of Mathematics. Furthermore, it is critical to consider the availability of computer technology and an internet connection when integrating and utilizing it as a platform for teaching and learning, and it has been suggested that students, teachers, and administrators are open and willing to integrate blended learning and teaching using a learning management system such as Quipper School despite a lack of access to and availability of technology. [28]

Effectiveness of Quipper as Learning Management System

Quipper School is one of the learning innovations that is expected to help students with learning difficulties. Quipper School is an online platform that makes use of the internet. Quipper School, as a Learning Management System (LMS), includes several features that assist teachers in designing learning and assisting students in understanding the lessons. Teachers can use various combinations of teaching materials such as texts, e-books, videos, pictures, graphs, and links to other online learning resources to deliver subject matter content. Students can select teaching materials that will help them understand the material better. [29]

In a study, it was shown that the academic performance of students is improved by the Quipper School. There is a significant difference between the two groups' academic performances, proving the Quipper School's effectiveness. Furthermore, following treatment, the experimental group evaluated the feasibility of using the Quipper School in terms of accessibility, cost, and time to use. Quipper School was rated as usable by respondents. [30]

Moreover, the Quipper application was used to assess the efficacy of the blended learning modality. Blended learning refers to an instructional model that combines traditional classroom practice with e-learning solutions. Quipper Philippines has collaborated with the Department of Education to provide teachers with a platform where they can access a content library, send ready-made lessons, quizzes, and exams, and receive real-time data on student performance. It was shown from a study that with the use of Quipper application, students' performance in blended learning modality was improved. [31]

The use of Quipper School aims to transform the way people learn and share knowledge by utilizing mobile internet [32]. Teachers use Quipper School to vary their instructional strategies [33]. Students' knowledge through a variety of ways, and Quipper School provides a fun way to learn online. Electronic grading eliminates all paperwork, and you can create a class and assignments easily. This will save both the teacher and the student's time and effort. Furthermore, Quipper School is free to use. It

is one form of interactive e-learning [30]. As a result, the presence of various facilities is expected to aid students in improving their understanding of scientific concepts [29].

II. METHODS

This study employed quantitative-descriptive design through survey method. This research design was deemed appropriate as it describes the characteristics of population or phenomenon studied, particularly the learning management system by the college faculty teachers at Saint Paul University Surigao (SPUS) in Surigao City, Philippines.

Thirty-three (33) college faculty members of SPUS for academic year 2022-2023 were purposefully chosen as respondents of the study. Researcher-made instruments were utilized as research instruments subjected to careful validation from experts in the field of research, statistics, language, and education. Before the conduct and data collection of the study, approval letters from the college Deans of SPUS were sought. Each respondent was rest assured that the gathered information shall be used solely for research purposes.

Frequency count, percentage, mean (M), and standard deviation (SD) were used for descriptive statistical analysis of the data. After a careful checking of the normality of the data, both parametric and non-parametric tests such as independent sample t-test, one-way ANOVA, Kruskal Wallis test, and Mann Whitney test were employed for inferential statistical analysis at 0.05 significance level, as some of the data were found to be not normally distributed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents with respects to age, sex, highest education attainment and number of years teaching. Most of them were females. The share of female teachers is continuing to rise, as this is widely acknowledged. According to World Bank data, 87.54% of primary school teachers in the Philippines are female as of 2016. This proves that the percentage of women in the teaching profession appears to be steadily increasing, and teaching is a female-dominated profession.

In terms of age, most of the respondents are between the ages of 30-39. Accordingly, young Filipino teachers mentioned their goals for their classrooms, including bringing about positive change, preparing students for life, inspiring others, promoting values, transforming lives, teaching out of passion, raising the bar for educational excellence, resolving social issues, sharing knowledge and skills, and enabling others to realize their dreams. [34]

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables		Frequency (n=33)	%
Sex	Male	13	39
	Female	20	61
Age	20-29	9	27
	30-39	12	37
	40-49	7	21
	50-above	5	15
Department	CECA	18	55
	CBT	5	15
	COE	3	9
	CHS	6	18
	CCJE	1	3
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	4	12
	Master's Degree	20	61
	Doctorate Degree	9	27
Number of Years in Teaching	1-10	15	46
	11-20	10	30
	21-above	8	24

When it came to the department, College of Education, Culture & Arts (CECA) obtained the highest frequency and the highest level of education attained by respondents was a master's degree. In terms of the number of years of teaching, majority of them taught for 1-10 years. Accordingly, teachers with at least ten years of experience are better at managing the classroom and are more capable of teaching. Furthermore, the more years of teaching experience a teacher has, the higher their self-efficacy to engage students and manage classrooms. [35]

In Table 2, under curriculum and assignment, results show that the teachers have the opportunity to develop their use of Quipper and with easy access to a student's profile. Teachers can also work constantly to improve the areas they need to enhance. Quipper lessens the workload of teachers by simplifying assignment management. This also helps faculty teachers to distribute and analyze homework more efficiently, as well as pay more attention to individual students. Quipper School gives teachers the tools they need to focus on providing quality education for future generations. [36]

On the other hand, it is evident in the results that the use of Quipper is limited to accessing the subject content, quizzes, exams and other activities of students. Quipper School's ability to provide reliable materials helps teachers and students deal with limited time. Quipper School is assumed to provide benefits such as score analysis, deadline setting, reliable materials, and feedback provision. [37]

Furthermore, this platform can be used by all faculty teachers and learners who require additional learning materials and exercises in which they can motivate their students to learn through Quipper School, particularly for practicing listening skills because limited time prevents them from practicing listening in the classroom. Generally, the level of utilization of Quipper as a learning management system to curriculum and assignments was verbally interpreted as "Often" and qualitatively described as "Utilized". In order to achieve a specific educational goal, a curriculum is a set of planning, strategy, and rules about the objectives, contents, materials, and teaching and learning process. [36]

In terms of the dimension statistics, Table 2 shows that Quipper is good in tracking and recording as it assesses or summarizes student data and makes it easy to see progress. Quipper allows teachers to monitor their student's engagement with the task and evaluate their achievements, particularly in the areas of student learning. Teachers can also use the due date strategy to raise students' awareness of their responsibilities. Students try to fulfill their responsibilities by submitting tasks on time. [37]

Table 2. Level of Utilization of the College Teachers on Quipper as a Learning Management System

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
Curriculum and Assignment				
I make use of Quipper to browse courses available in school.	2.70	0.85	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper to navigate the General Education subject' Student Content and School Courses.	2.70	0.88	Often	Utilized
I maximize the use of Quipper to create an assignment and select topics in the Curriculum.	2.88	0.89	Often	Utilized
I select and search for the specific topics or activities for students' access easily since these are already categorized.	2.88	0.89	Often	Utilized
I manipulate classes for self-study.	2.85	0.87	Often	Utilized
I resort to Quipper because General Education subjects are displayed so I can openly access the subject content, quizzes, exams and other activities.	2.64	0.96	Often	Utilized
Average	2.77	0.89	Often	Utilized
Statistics				
I use Quipper, which allows me to see the statistics of students learned.	2.94	1.00	Often	Utilized

I use Quipper to view statistics for assignments and examinations in all subjects.	2.97	1.02	Often	Utilized
I apply and assist to view statistics from all periods by setting the date.	2.97	1.02	Often	Utilized
I find Quipper functional when working on the statistical report and send the results through teachers' email.	2.97	1.02	Often	Utilized
Average	2.96	1.00	Often	Utilized
Classlist				
I use Quipper especially when I create classes with class codes for students.	3.18	0.98	Often	Utilized
I exploit Quipper to see detailed class information.	2.97	0.95	Often	Utilized
I limit monitoring classes in Quipper using the class codes.	2.91	0.91	Often	Utilized
I modify the details of the class if needed and assign a color scheme which will be reflected on the home screen.	2.82	0.95	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper to monitor the status or the progress of the students' tasks, whether completed, in progress or not started in the viewing details.	3.06	0.93	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper, for links to download class reports of students' performance in the class and by request, the system allows me to show summary scores, whether first attempt or highest scores and group students, whether male or female.	3.03	0.92	Often	Utilized
I maximize the use of Quipper to search for creating assignments for students.	2.91	0.95	Often	Utilized
Quipper is useful to discern as I am provided with the summary of login and out for the past days of the students.	2.79	0.89	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper to list live classes and create new live classes and their zoom account and authorize Quipper to access it on their behalf.	2.70	0.88	Often	Utilized
Average	2.93	0.93	Often	Utilized
Students				
I use Quipper to type class names and select classes and search for the first and last names of the students.	3.06	0.97	Often	Utilized
I maximize the use of Quipper to monitor students' progress in all attempted topics and assignments in the overview section, which includes time spent on videos, topics completed, and number of questions answered.	3.03	0.92	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper to monitor the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first and last attempt scores.	3.03	0.92	Often	Utilized

I navigate students' individual performance in class on the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first and last attempt score.	3.03	0.92	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper when I change password in the class for security measures and change students' names.	3.00	1.00	Often	Utilized
Average	3.03	0.93	Often	Utilized
Q-create				
Quipper is functional when I am creating courses, checking its publication status, and publication date.	3.00	0.97	Often	Utilized
I use the Quipper to check the course list and create topics.	3.09	0.98	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper since it allows me to create topic names.	3.12	0.96	Often	Utilized
I use Quipper to create questions, upload files to create a text page, create a page.	3.18	0.95	Often	Utilized
I employ Quipper to shuffle questions for assignments and shuffle choices automatically and assign quiz titles.	3.18	0.95	Often	Utilized
Quipper allows me to import and create questions.	3.12	0.93	Often	Utilized
I utilize Quipper to download my study guides and add more files.	3.03	0.95	Often	Utilized
Average	3.11	0.95	Often	Utilized
Grand Mean	2.96	0.94	Often	Utilized

Legend:

Parameters	Verbal Interpretation (VI)	Qualitative Description (QD)
3.25 – 4.00	Always	Highly Utilized
2.50 – 3.24	Often	Utilized
1.75 – 2.49	Rarely	Less Utilized
1.00 – 1.74	Never	Not Utilized

As to classlist, Table 2 shows a good result for Quipper as LMS. Which, by creating a code, it would be easy for teachers to communicate and disseminate their lessons and tasks to students. A teacher can create a virtual class in Quipper and then give access to students so they can log in using unique class codes. Teachers can monitor any student activity via the Quipper school application, and students' assignments can be monitored at any time, as can anyone who has begun work, done nothing, or completed work. However, teachers using Quipper should be more dynamic so as to utilize it as a tool to help with learning activities. Teachers can create lessons that their students can access. Despite the availability of an administrative system, Quipper does not provide an administrative function. Teachers must therefore create a new classroom (course), create learning modules, and select the students who will participate. This administrative task may be difficult for some teachers, especially those who are unfamiliar with a web-based learning management system. [16,38]

When it comes to students, Table 2 shows that teachers can quickly access the classes of his or her pupils so that they can assess the student's development. E-learning is a learning process that employs electronic devices to transmit content in order to function easily and support interactive learning that can be done anytime and anywhere. But it should be noted that it is crucial to protect user privacy and maintain secure accounts. Students could not reasonably object to such data surveillance because it was taking place in educational environments like virtual classrooms. Most of this monitoring was done privately, without the student's

awareness or consent. Some teachers did not give their students the option to decline to be tracked. Most of the time, children could not opt out of such observation without also choosing to skip obligatory teaching and all formal education. [39,40]

Finally, for Q-create dimension, Table 2 reveals that teachers can utilize Quipper to push students' capacity since it is creative and innovative in learning knowledge. Quipper is a ready-to-use web-based learning tool for teachers and students. It also helps teachers by providing data storage for their PowerPoint presentations, PDF files, photographs, and videos. Furthermore, by maintaining their teaching and learning activities on the web server, teachers can keep track of their student's progress without being constrained by time or place. Furthermore, Quipper School media resources are great options for use as a tool for teaching and learning about environmental change materials. Quipper School media is also a viable option as a tool to enhance learning management. [16,41]

In Table 3, the results indicated that the college teachers are satisfied with using Quipper to create assignments for students since the application already provided the material they needed. The implementation of Quipper School in English teaching was seen as something good and helpful for the teacher because it provided the material and tasks that the teacher required, eliminating the need for them to create any. Generally, the result shows that the teachers are satisfied in using Quipper as to curriculum and assignments since it allows them to create assignments, quizzes, examinations, and other activities. [27]

In terms of the dimension statistics, Table 3 shows that teachers are satisfied with how Quipper assists them in analyzing students' progress. Another advantage of Quipper is about scoring. It was already done automatically by the application after each task. As a result, a teacher would not have to assess the tasks of the students herself. Quipper School is known to be different from other traditional educational websites because of its attributes that enable teachers to evaluate the students' scores. Teachers could ascertain the range of the student's scores and monitor the progress of students' outcomes. He can also analyze scores lower than the MCM as the consideration for giving students remedial assignments. [27,42]

As to classlist, Table 3 shows how pleased the college teachers were with Quipper when creating new classes because the system instantly generates a unique "class code." Accordingly, the teacher could create an online class and invite students to participate based on the code of each class, which students could access at any time and from any location. The teachers can use LINK's Live Class feature to create synchronous classes and can connect with students on a Zoom Meeting directly through the Q-Link platform without creating a Zoom account. [39,43]

Table 3. Level of Satisfaction of the College Teachers on Quipper as a Learning Management System

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
Curriculum and Assignment				
I make use of Quipper to browse courses available in school.	2.97	0.85	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper to navigate the General Education subject' Student Content and School Courses.	2.94	0.86	Often	Satisfied
I maximize the use of Quipper to create an assignment and select topics in the Curriculum.	3.03	0.85	Often	Satisfied
I select and search for the specific topics or activities for students' access easily since these are already categorized.	2.97	0.77	Often	Satisfied
I manipulate classes for self-study.	3.00	0.75	Often	Satisfied
I resort to Quipper because General Education subjects are displayed so I can openly access the subject content, quizzes, exams and other activities.	2.97	0.85	Often	Satisfied
Average	2.98	0.81	Often	Satisfied
Statistics				
I use Quipper, which allows me to see the statistics	3.03	0.92	Often	Satisfied

of students learned.				
I use Quipper to view statistics for assignments and examinations in all subjects.	2.97	0.92	Often	Satisfied
I apply and assist to view statistics from all periods by setting the date.	2.94	0.90	Often	Satisfied
I find Quipper functional when working on the statistical report and send the results through teachers' email.	2.97	0.88	Often	Satisfied
Average	2.98	0.89	Often	Satisfied
Classlist				
I use Quipper especially when I create classes with class codes for students.	3.09	0.80	Often	Satisfied
I exploit Quipper to see detailed class information.	3.03	0.77	Often	Satisfied
I limit monitoring classes in Quipper using the class codes.	3.03	0.85	Often	Satisfied
I modify the details of the class if needed and assign a color scheme which will be reflected on the home screen.	3.03	0.81	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper to monitor the status or the progress of the students' tasks, whether completed, in progress or not started in the viewing details.	3.06	0.83	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper, for links to download class reports of students' performance in the class and by request, the system allows me to show summary scores, whether first attempt or highest scores and group students, whether male or female.	2.97	0.81	Often	Satisfied
I maximize the use of Quipper to search for creating assignments for students.	2.82	0.85	Often	Satisfied
Quipper is useful to discern as I am provided with the summary of login and out for the past days of the students.	2.76	0.83	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper to list live classes and create new live classes and their zoom account and authorize Quipper to access it on their behalf.	2.76	0.94	Often	Satisfied
Average	2.95	0.83	Often	Satisfied
Students				
I use Quipper to type class names and select classes and search for the first and last names of the students.	2.97	0.81	Often	Satisfied
I maximize the use of Quipper to monitor students' progress in all attempted topics and assignments in the overview section, which includes time spent on videos, topics completed, and number of questions answered.	2.91	0.91	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper to monitor the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first	2.97	0.92	Often	Satisfied

and last attempt scores.				
I navigate students' individual performance in class on the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first and last attempt score.	3.06	0.79	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper when I change password in the class for security measures and change students' names.	3.00	0.79	Often	Satisfied
Average	2.98	0.84	Often	Satisfied
Q-create				
Quipper is functional when I am creating courses, checking its publication status, and publication date.	3.06	0.79	Often	Satisfied
I use the Quipper to check the course list and create topics.	3.12	0.82	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper since it allows me to create topic names.	3.12	0.82	Often	Satisfied
I use Quipper to create questions, upload files to create a text page, create a page.	3.18	0.85	Often	Satisfied
I employ Quipper to shuffle questions for assignments and shuffle choices automatically and assign quiz titles.	3.12	0.82	Often	Satisfied
Quipper allows me to import and create questions.	3.21	0.78	Often	Satisfied
I utilize Quipper to download my study guides and add more files.	3.21	0.82	Often	Satisfied
Average	3.15	0.76	Often	Satisfied
Grand Mean	3.01	0.83	Often	Satisfied

Legend:

Parameters	Verbal Interpretation (VI)	Qualitative Description (QD)
3.25 – 4.00	Always	Highly Satisfied
2.50 – 3.24	Often	Satisfied
1.75 – 2.49	Rarely	Less Satisfied
1.00 – 1.74	Never	Not Satisfied

When it comes to students, Table 3 shows the satisfaction among college faculty with how the system assists them to see the progress and score of each quiz attempt by tapping the record. Quipper offers an assessment program that allows teachers to evaluate and monitor the progress of their students. In fact, Quipper School was created to make learning easier, and it assists teachers in task preparation and student progress monitoring. Furthermore, Table 3 revealed the fulfillment of the teachers towards using Quipper. Quipper School documented all of the activities students participated in for strengthening material and quiz training which allow them to track their students' learning performances using the platform, enabling them to become more adaptive in the lesson plans and materials they prepare to help their students. [37,39]

For Q-create, Table 3 shows the fulfillment that Quipper offers to the teacher. In fact, a study about Utilizing Quipper School for improving reading comprehension of recent text showed that the teacher can utilize a Q-Create account to post their own test questions to her students. The Quipper code was used to send the question to the student. This enables students to open and respond to the specified test questions. These results show that the college faculty are satisfied with Q-Create which allows them to pick exercises for the students and also shows all the activities that the student missed to access or answer before the due date. [44]

Table 4. Level of Effectiveness of the College Teachers on Quipper as a Learning Management System

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
Curriculum and Assignment				
I make use of Quipper to browse courses available in school.	3.00	0.75	Often	Effective
I use Quipper to navigate the General Education subject' Student Content and School Courses.	2.82	0.81	Often	Effective
I maximize the use of Quipper to create an assignment and select topics in the Curriculum.	2.97	0.73	Often	Effective
I select and search for the specific topics or activities for students' access easily since these are already categorized.	3.00	0.75	Often	Effective
I manipulate classes for self-study.	3.15	0.76	Often	Effective
I resort to Quipper because General Education subjects are displayed so I can openly access the subject content, quizzes, exams and other activities.	3.06	0.83	Often	Effective
Average	3.00	0.77	Often	Effective
Statistics				
I use Quipper, which allows me to see the statistics of students learned.	3.00	0.83	Often	Effective
I use Quipper to view statistics for assignments and examinations in all subjects.	3.03	0.77	Often	Effective
I apply and assist to view statistics from all periods by setting the date.	3.03	0.77	Often	Effective
I find Quipper functional when working on the statistical report and send the results through teachers' email.	3.06	0.77	Often	Effective
Average	3.03	0.78	Often	Effective
Classlist				
I use Quipper especially when I create classes with class codes for students.	3.03	0.77	Often	Effective
I exploit Quipper to see detailed class information.	3.12	0.78	Often	Effective
I limit monitoring classes in Quipper using the class codes.	3.12	0.74	Often	Effective
I modify the details of the class if needed and assign a color scheme which will be reflected on the home screen.	2.97	0.73	Often	Effective
I use Quipper to monitor the status or the progress of the students' tasks, whether completed, in progress or not started in the viewing details.	3.12	0.70	Often	Effective
I use Quipper, for links to download class reports of students' performance in the class and by request, the system allows me to show summary scores, whether first attempt or highest scores and group students, whether male or female.	3.15	0.71	Often	Effective
I maximize the use of Quipper to search for creating assignments for students.	3.03	0.64	Often	Effective
Quipper is useful to discern as I am provided with the summary of login and out for the past days of the students.	3.00	0.75	Often	Effective

I use Quipper to list live classes and create new live classes and their zoom account and authorize Quipper to access it on their behalf.	2.97	0.73	Often	Effective
Average	3.06	0.72	Often	Effective
Students				
I use Quipper to type class names and select classes and search for the first and last names of the students.	3.03	0.73	Often	Effective
I maximize the use of Quipper to monitor students' progress in all attempted topics and assignments in the overview section, which includes time spent on videos, topics completed, and number of questions answered.	3.03	0.73	Often	Effective
I use Quipper to monitor the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first and last attempt scores.	3.00	0.71	Often	Effective
I navigate students' individual performance in class on the topics with video watching, time spent on videos, quiz attempts, first and last attempt score.	3.03	0.73	Often	Effective
I use Quipper when I change password in the class for security measures and change students' names.	3.06	0.70	Often	Effective
Average	3.03	0.71	Often	Effective
Q-create				
I find the Quipper effectual when I create courses, check its publication status, and publication date.	3.06	0.75	Often	Effective
Quipper is functional when I published and unpublished the created topic.	3.00	0.79	Often	Effective
Quipper is advantageous when I check the course list and create topics.	3.12	0.74	Often	Effective
I find Quipper helpful when I create topic names.	3.12	0.74	Often	Effective
I find Quipper worth the time when I create questions, upload files to create a text page, create a page and preview the topic.	3.09	0.77	Often	Effective
I find Quipper functional since it permits me to shuffle questions for assignments and shuffle choices automatically.	3.00	0.71	Often	Effective
I find Quipper effective to import and create questions.	3.06	0.70	Often	Effective
I find Quipper efficient for downloading study guides and adding more files.	2.97	0.68	Often	Effective
Average	3.05	0.73	Often	Effective
Grand Mean	3.03	0.74	Often	Effective

Legend:

Parameters	Verbal Interpretation (VI)	Qualitative Description (QD)
3.25 – 4.00	Always	Highly Effective
2.50 – 3.24	Often	Effective
1.75 – 2.49	Rarely	Less Effective
1.00 – 1.74	Never	Not Effective

From Table 4, it was revealed that Quipper is deemed effective to create classes and give assignments. Teachers find Quipper’s system as effective as they can monitor the progress of their students. Using the 'assignment' menu, teachers can create new tasks, assign them to students, and track their progress. Teachers made extensive use of Quipper because it provides a customizable method for them to distribute projects and administer exams while saving time and effort. Some learning management systems do not offer the Quipper method, which requires teachers to put forth extra effort to assign work to every class. [11]

Additionally, the assessment of the teachers makes it clear that they effectively determined the statistics and records of their student’s output through Quipper’s Statistics feature. These results support the idea that learning management systems' detailed reports should be available, so both administrators and learners can view records of test scores. Administrators should be able to generate detailed reports about overall learner performance. Users can view their own progress and see how close they are to their goal of completing the course. [35]

The variable Classlist in the level of effectiveness of Quipper as a learning management system as assessed by the college faculty of St. Paul University Surigao got the verbal interpretation of “Often” and qualitative description of “Effective” which implies that through an LMS, the need for one system to accommodate all learning styles and levels can be met. Teachers effectively organize their classes and post different documents, assignments, tests, etc. for their students to work on without the students knowing they are receiving something that has been specifically developed for their own level. Thus, with an LMS, communication increases. Groups are developed within the system for sharing resources, sending messages, and connecting with staff and students. Club teachers can have separate groups where information is easily distributed and visible to the members of the club.

The administration can post quick messages and instructions and celebrate successes on the LMS, where staff can view the information with ease and without crowding email inboxes. Moreover, educators can join community groups, connect with other educators, post questions, and learn from others outside the school community. Accordingly, as with any website, LMS portals are exposed to information security threats. Hackers could have gained access to student information. Open LMS stated that protecting user data and sensitive information in your Learning Management System (LMS) should be taken very seriously. E-learning security is essential in preventing costly regulatory penalties around incidents related to leaked personal information, confidential organizational data, or other potential security risks. [45,46,47]

Table 5. Test of Significant Difference in the Levels of Utilization, Satisfaction, Effectiveness of Quipper when grouped based on Respondents’ Profile

Profile Variables	Dependent Variables	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Level of Utilization	0.253	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Satisfaction	0.347	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Effectiveness	0.480	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Age	Level of Utilization	0.930	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Satisfaction	0.803	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Effectiveness	0.575	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Department	Level of Utilization	0.087	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Satisfaction	0.110	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Effectiveness	0.011	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	Level of Utilization	0.174	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Satisfaction	0.141	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Effectiveness	0.644	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	Level of Utilization	0.562	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Satisfaction	0.520	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Level of Effectiveness	0.950	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant

Table 5 shows that there were significant differences in the levels of utilization and satisfaction of Quipper when the respondents are grouped based on their profile. Also, there was no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of Quipper when the respondents are grouped based on profile, except for department. This means that the teachers’ assessment on the effectiveness of Quipper as LMS significantly differs when grouped based on the department where they belong. The exposure and training received by teachers per department as to how to utilize and navigate Quipper as a school’s LMS may have contributed to this result. This suggests that each department should have in depth Quipper’s training and workshop for teachers so that all faculty members across all departments will have a meaningful and fruitful experience in using Quipper.

Table 6. Test of Significant Relationship among the Levels of Utilization, Satisfaction, Effectiveness of Quipper

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of Utilization	Level of Satisfaction	0.805	0.0001	Reject null hypothesis	Significant Positive Relationship
	Level of Effectiveness	0.692	0.0001	Reject null hypothesis	Significant Positive Relationship
Level of Satisfaction	Level of Effectiveness	0.839	0.0001	Reject null hypothesis	Significant Positive Relationship

Table 6 shows that there were significant positive relationships between the respondents’ level of utilization and level of satisfaction, between the level of utilization and level of effectiveness, and between the level of effectiveness and level of satisfaction. This suggests that as faculty members utilize Quipper often, their level of satisfaction and Quipper’s level of effectiveness will also increase, and vice versa.

In addition, when the level of effectiveness of Quipper as LMS increases, the respondents’ level of satisfaction will also increase, and vice versa. The utilization of a learning management system (LMS) is beneficial for faculty and student learning in higher education, offering effective classroom management, flexibility in teaching and grading, accessible learning resources, and facilitating communication between students and faculty. It can positively impact student learning, teaching, and institutional effectiveness, and adopting a user-friendly LMS can contribute to student learning and decision-making in college education.

Accordingly, the use of technology in education such as learning management systems (LMS) has become imperative. The LMS includes a full spectrum of tools that provides academic and learning institutions with an effective and efficient means to support distance learning courses. Instructors’ satisfaction is essential for the deployment of LMS. The success of LMS in any institution starts with instructors’ satisfaction, which in turn initiates and promotes learners’ utilization of LMS. [48]

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

According to the study’s findings, variables such as sex, age, department, highest educational attainment, and years of teaching experience among teachers do not significantly influence the level of utilization and satisfaction with Quipper. Similarly, the profile of college faculty members, including their sex, age, highest educational attainment, and years of teaching, does not have a significant impact on the effectiveness of Quipper as a learning management system. The study revealed that the department variable does affect how well Quipper performs as a learning management system, according to college faculty teachers’ evaluations. It was observed that faculty members at Saint Paul University Surigao who utilize Quipper frequently tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction, leading to an increase in Quipper’s effectiveness. Conversely, as Quipper’s effectiveness as an LMS increases, participants’ satisfaction levels also rise. The study indicates that Quipper is widely utilized, effective, and satisfies the needs of the college faculty members at Saint Paul University Surigao.

While the study demonstrated that SPUS college faculty have found Quipper to be effective and satisfying as a learning management system in their classes, there are still opportunities for improvement. The administration could establish clear goals for the successful implementation of Quipper as a learning management system. Incentives or awards may be provided to teachers who consistently use Quipper, and proper training and guidance should be offered to familiarize teachers with Quipper’s functions and tools. Encouraging teachers to attend seminars and training sessions could enhance their interest in exploring more of

Quipper's features. Since Quipper has been proven effective and satisfying when utilized, all teachers should be encouraged to use it. This would enable teachers to better understand students' struggles and provide supplementary materials to support their learning in specific lessons.

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